

Table 1: Action Risk Identification

Action	Risk Identification
When? (Session)	First Sprint Planning (recommended) and during the Sprint execution.
As? (Detail)	<p>First Sprint Planning, the team can identify an initial set of risks for the target project, creating the Risk Register for the Target Project. For this activity, the manager uses the recommendation system to assist in decision-making in identifying risks for the target project.</p> <p>During sprint execution: The Target Project Risk Register can be updated at any time by the Scrum team, with support from the Risk Manager.</p>
Input	Target project characteristics (for the recommender system) and Tacit Knowledge of the professionals.
Output	Target Project Risk Register with elicited risks and possible mitigations.
Responsible Person	Risk Manager and the Team.

Table 2: Action Risk Assessment and Strategies

Action	Risk Assessment and Strategies
When? (Session)	The Risk Supervisor must facilitate this meeting whenever they deem it necessary.
As? (Detail)	<p>Analyze and Evaluate such risks, probabilities, impacts, and mitigation and response plans. If necessary, update the risk register template of the target project (i.e., change the status of risks already identified or add new risks).</p> <p>Implement a Mitigation (if convenient) and Response plan (if the risk materializes), referring to the risks raised.</p> <p>Consult and monitor the risks raised, evaluating whether the analysis is valid and whether the mitigation and response plans remain correct.</p> <p>If any risk has materialized, assess its impact on the delivery of the product and record it in the project risk register.</p>
Input	Target Project Risk Register
Output	Target Project Risk Register (Updated)
Responsible Person	Risk Supervisor

Table 3: Action Critical Risk Analysis

Action	Critical Risk Analysis
When? (Session)	Sprint Retrospective (Recommended)
As? (Detail)	<p>It consists of the effort to maintain the quality of the corporate database. At the end of each sprint, when there are new risk records, the Risk Manager must validate them and save them in the corporate risk memory to ensure that the language is adequate and the information is consistent.</p>
Input	Target Project Risk Register
Output	Updated Organization Database
Responsible Person	Risk Manager